

DYNAMICS OF VOID FORMATION UPON CURING OF EPOXY RESIN

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SUMMARY: The role of internal stresses in the formation of voids during cure of neat epoxy resin and fibre reinforced epoxy has been identified. The combined evolution of the modulus and of the volume shrinkage often leads to voiding when the resin is constrained during cure. To analyse this phenomenon, the shrinkage of an epoxy resin was studied in a constrained volume. Void initiation was observed at two different stages during isothermal cure, before gelation and around or after gelation. A corresponding critical internal stress at void initiation was calculated by viscoelastic analysis. This stress criterion is used to construct a process window for production of void-free composites.

KEYWORDS: void formation, internal stresses, process window

INTRODUCTION

Prepreg lay-up and autoclave cure is one of several important processes used in obtaining high quality fibre reinforced thermoset composite structures. High temperature and high pressure are usually used to reduce the resin viscosity and to suppress voids during the consolidation of the composite. One of the major concerns during composite processing is therefore to control the formation of defects such as voids in the resin. Four different mechanisms have been identified as the cause of such defects. They include: (1) mechanical trapping of air between plies during the lamination process, (2) diffusion of dissolved water and gases in the resin, (3) formation of volatiles in the resin during cure, and (4) increase of resin stress due to the chemical shrinkage under constrained boundary conditions. Mechanisms (1), (2), and (3) have been observed and investigated quite extensively [1-2], and practical solutions have been provided to prevent their occurrence. Void formation due to mechanically entrapped air can for example be solved by the handling skills of the workers and by the implementation of an air path during the lamination process. Proper storage of the prepregs and a careful choice as to the resin composition, can significantly reduce both the diffusion of dissolved and absorbed water and the formation of volatiles, as they both depend greatly on the chemical characteristics of the resin and on its handling before and during processing.

The last mechanism, namely void formation due to the increase of resin stress under constrained boundary conditions, has been reported in the literature but never quantified. This is the objective of the present study. An indirect method is proposed, whereby a sample of resin is cured in a closed transparent mould. The location and time at which a void forms were experimentally observed during cure. The level of internal stress in the resin corresponding to the time of the void formation was then calculated by a Boltzmann superposition principle, based on the viscoelastic mechanical properties and the measured chemical shrinkage of the resin during cure. The viscoelastic modulus of the epoxy resin was evaluated using the time-cure-temperature

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superposition principle [3]. The strain change of epoxy resin due to the chemical shrinkage was measured and expressed by a numerical expression as a function of cure temperature and conversion [4]. A criterion defining the critical stress for the void initiation was therefore proposed. To enable the production of void-free composite laminates, a process window was then constructed, based on the critical stress for a void initiation. The window was constructed as a function of the fibre volume fraction, the stacking sequence and the applied pressure during the autoclave cure.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The resin system chosen for this study was comprised of tetra glycidly-4, 4'-diaminodiphenyl-methane epoxy (TGDDM, MY720, Ciba Geigy) and anthranilic acid amide curing agent (AAA, Fluka Co.). The resin system is mixed at a ratio of 43.54 parts of curing agent per hundred parts of resin (phr) by weight. The crystalline curing agent was dissolved in the liquid epoxy monomer at 100°C. With vigorous stirring, complete dissolution took place within 10 minutes. This procedure was adopted in order to ensure homogeneous mixing and to avoid the use of a solvent. Immediately after mixing, the resin was degassed under vacuum at 80°C for 5 minutes. A glass cylinder with a length of 90mm and an inside diameter of 5mm was filled with the liquid epoxy and sealed with a glass cap. It was then turned upside down and placed in an oven at the given cure temperatures. Void formation was visually observed and recorded on a video camera. For prepregging, thin sheets of unidirectional E-glass were impregnated with epoxy resin on a hot plate at 80°C. The gelation point of the epoxy system was taken at the storage and loss modulus crossover point according to ASTM D4473-90. For the autoclave cure of stacked prepregs, three kind of stacking sequences were used: $[0_5]_T$, $[0/90_3/0]_T$ and $[0/90/0/90/0]_T$. The stacked prepregs were cured at different stacking sequences in the autoclave with different pressures. Cross sections of the laminates cured at different pressures were observed using an optical microscope to locate and measure the dimensions of the voids.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Void formation in a curing epoxy resin

Due to the cure induced shrinkage of the resin and the volume constraint exerted by the glass cylinder, two types of voids appeared at different times during isothermal cure, as shown in Fig. 1. With increasing conversion at a given cure temperature, a first void appears in the resin; this void then moves up to the top of the glass cylinder due to a buoyancy effect and the relatively low viscosity of the resin. This first void grows with the volumetric shrinkage of the resin, but its growth is stopped at around gelation point. Subsequently a second void appears around gelation within the closed glass tube. The value of conversion of the epoxy resin at the first and second void formation based on cure history, was calculated by a kinetic model developed in a previous study [3]. The internal stress levels in the resin under constrained volume during isothermal cure, were calculated using the Boltzmann superposition principle with the combined shrinkage and modulus evolution.

Fig. 1: Sketch of the first and second voids initiation.

Fig. 2: Critical internal stresses, conversion and void initiations in the epoxy as a function of cure temperature at the second void initiation.

The first void which appears at low conversions will tend to escape by buoyancy but the second void, appearing close to gelation, will remain as a defect within the resin. The second void initiation is thus considered to be a critical phenomena in the curing process of epoxy resin. The critical internal stresses and conversions calculated at each cure temperature, which correspond to the time at second void initiation from experiments, are shown in Fig. 2. This indicates that the critical conversion at second void initiation increases linearly whilst the critical stress increases in the logarithmic scale of stress with increasing cure temperature. This average critical stress can be considered as being one of the material properties for void initiation around the gelation point.

Composite application

As long as no voids are formed during cure, the volume of composite decreases with the decrease of the resin volume due to chemical shrinkage, whilst the fibre volume remains constant. At the same time, the stress on the fibre network increases, as a result of decrease in composite volume. Because the composite pressure is constant and equal to the applied pressure, the resin pressure decreases. In practice, at the beginning of cure, the resin is liquid and does not as yet adhere to the fibres and its volume therefore decreases. As the composite pressure is maintained constant, this release of resin pressure is taken up by the fibre network. Thus, as conversion increases, the fibre stress increases and the resin pressure decreases. This overall volume contraction goes on until complete cure unless the fibre stress reaches the external pressure. The resin would then tend to shrink more, pulling the fibres even closer together. This would, however, result in resin voiding, as the strength of the resin is very low at the cure temperature. Hence, the resin cures in a constrained environment mould. If the conversion is still low at that stage, the resin shrinks and voids which are formed before the gelation (first void) may immediately appear in the resin. If the conversion is high enough (close to gelation), the resin is constrained and develops tensile internal stress, until it reaches the maximum allowed stress defined by the criterion obtained from the critical stress at second void formation. Therefore, during conversion, internal stresses in the resin are initially compressive due to the applied pressure, but will increase to possibly reach a tensile state and cross the void initiation criterion.

Fig. 3: Fibre volume fraction changes of stacked dry glass fibres as a function of applied pressure.

The formation of voids can thus be controlled by the level of applied pressure in the autoclave. Results from the stacked fibre network compression test are given in Fig. 3. The fibre volume fractions rapidly increase with increasing applied pressure up to 2 bar, and keep almost constant values in each stacking sequence. A processing window was then constructed, from the results of the fibre volume fraction as a function of applied pressure, volume shrinkage of the resin and critical criterion at void formation. This was done, in order to avoid the formation of voids taking

into account the fibre volume fraction and applied pressure from the autoclave. The processing window for void free composites together with experimental results of void formation for produced composites are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Process window and experimental results of void formation of unidirectional glass/epoxy fibre composites, $[0/90/0/90/0]_T$, as a function of fibre volume fraction.

The calculated critical pressure needed to suppress the formation of voids is compared to the measured void content for different laminates. If the applied pressure on the laminates is greater than the calculated critical pressure for void formation, then the laminates should be free from voids. This has indeed been verified for different lay-ups and fibre volume fractions. For example, 54(9) in Fig. 4 means that there are 9 voids with an average diameter of 54 μ m.

Fig. 5: Micrographs of the unidirectional glass/epoxy laminate cross section, (a) $v_f = 0.54$, 3 bar of applied pressure; (b) $v_f = 0.54$, 1 bar of applied pressure; (c) $v_f = 0.62$, 5 bar of applied pressure ($[0/90/0/90/0]_T$)

Fig. 5 shows micrographs of the cross section of unidirectional glass/epoxy laminates ($[0/90/0/90/0]_T$) cured under different applied pressures, represented as experimental data points in Fig. 4. As expected, no voids were observed in the case of a low v_f (0.54) laminate cured at 3 bar (Fig. 5 (a)) since these conditions are well above the critical boundary line for void free composites. On the other hand many voids were observed in the two other laminates as shown in

Fig. 5 ($v_f=0.54$ and 1 bar, Fig. 5 (b); $v_f=0.62$ and 5 bar, Fig. 5 (c)). A good agreement is thus observed between experimental and calculated results. This approach can therefore be used to construct a processing window for the manufacture of laminates free of cure-induced voids.

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental technique was developed to observe void formation in epoxy systems during cure. This showed that a critical internal stress which is independent of the isothermal cure temperature can be used as a criterion for voids initiating at gelation. This critical value can be considered as one of the material properties for stress-initiated voids. This result was applied to composite processing. A process window with the aim at minimising internal stress levels and avoiding void formation during cure is presented. The internal stress was calculated by a new model taking into account the applied pressure during cure. This stress was compared to the critical stress for void initiation. A process window was thus constructed to indicate the allowed applied pressure as a function of the fibre volume fraction and the architecture of fibre networks during cure.

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